

chist-era

OPENMIN Project

Deliverable Number 2.1

Creating a prototype for an EMM Qualitative Studies Registry

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Task		2.1 Creating an EMM Qualitative Studies Registry			
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Publishable abstract		This document (Deliverable 2.1) includes out a detailed outline for an EMM qualitative studies registry within the existing Dataverse framework. The deliverable presents the design of a prototype, which was conceptualised during the OpenMin project. It delineates the inherent limitations of the prototype and any additional considerations that would be necessary when attempting to deploy such a tool in the future.			
Keywords		Open science, Open research data, Migration data, Metadata			

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1. Introduction

This document is a deliverable of the OPENMIN project, which is entitled "Consolidating Open Science and Data Initiatives on Ethnic and Migrant Minorities in Europe."

The subsequent deliverable pertains to the prototype of an EMM (Ethnic and Migrant Minorities) qualitative studies registry, which was contemplated and evaluated during the course of the project, utilising the prevailing Dataverse infrastructure furnished by AUSSDA (Austrian Social Science Data Archive). AUSSDA is the national CESSDA (Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives) ERIC associate.

The development of such a tool is considered to be of critical importance, as it would serve as a crucial component in the establishment of a comprehensive infrastructure within the EMM research domain. The implementation of this tool would enhance the visibility of studies within the field, foster collaboration, and facilitate the reuse of materials produced by these studies. This is particularly pertinent given that the existing EMM Survey Registry merely collects metadata on migration and minority-related survey studies, excluding data from other methodological areas and research methods, which are important for field.

Figure 1 - EMMSD² top level site, to be found at <https://data.aussda.at/dataverse/emmsd2>

The primary objective of this task (2.1) within OPENMIN was to identify a potential solution for researchers seeking to document metadata from diverse research forms at the same level of detail and quality as the current EMM survey registry permits. It is evident that the

development and provision of a controlled, FAIR-standards-compliant EMM qualitative studies registry tool would address a structural gap in the data infrastructure for EMM research. The objective is to build a tool that is based on a modified open-source version of the Harvard universe developed Dataverse infrastructure. However, due to limited resources, only a prototype could be developed, rather than a full tool. This is consistent with the project proposal and should facilitate the development of a comprehensive tool based on the insights acquired during the OPEN MIN project at a subsequent stage. A key insight generated by this task was also a scoping concerning the depth of qualitative studies based migration research in Austria, which allows to assess the actual need and potential benefits if such a tool could be fielded in the form of a production version in the future.

Disclaimer: For the creation of this document DEEPL was used for proofreading all text, as the authors are not speaking English as their first language.

Tool and service status	Prototype; can only be accessed from the University of Vienna, using the AUSSDA Dataverse development server
Service Owner	AUSSDA – the Austrian Social Science Data Archive
Legal Background for Operation	Austrian legal framework
Technical Officer	Christian Bischof (christian.bischof@univie.ac.at)
Project Officer	Jana C. Kern (jana.kern@jku.at)
Project Lead	Dimitri Prandner (dimitri.prandner@jku.at)
Data offered	Prandner, Dimitri; Kern, Jana (2025). <i>EMM Research Hub Austria (qualitative) (SUF edition)</i> , AUSSDA. https://doi.org/10.11587/ZZPCXX/XQQHPX (Metadata collection, based on the prototype)

Table 1 - Short overview

Outcomes:

<p>Main goal: Build and test a qualitative studies meta data registry for EMM projects.</p>	<p>Completed; as expected the tool is not operational, but relevant insights could be generated.</p>
<p>Subgoal:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Create a structure for a potential production version of a EMM qualitative studies registry • Collect data that may be used to fill such a registry. • Provide a landing page introducing the tool to potential users 	<p>The structure for the meta data collection was created and transferred into a manual, based on the work on the EMM Survey Registry, completed by Morales et al. (2021).</p> <p>Data for the registry was collected and compiled for the case of Austria. A dataset containing the compiled information can be found in the newly developed EMMSD² self-deposit tool.</p> <p>AUSSDA has created a dedicated landing page on its EMM project subpage. It will go online after confirmation after quality control via AUSSDA in Q1/2026.</p>

Figure 2 - Outcomes of task 2.1

2. Needs, Infrastructure, Hosting and Long-Term Data Preservation

The development of a prototype EMM Qualitative Studies Registry was initiated, as the implementation of such a tool would facilitate enhanced transparency and accessibility in qualitative migration and minority research. This is of relevance, as the domain of qualitative research projects and data collection constitutes a pivotal component of research dealing with issue relate to migration and minorities.

Nevertheless, this particular methodological field of research has historically proven to be a challenge to systematically explore, despite its strong ties to different research streams in migration. Indeed, over the 20th century and the early 21st century, research infrastructure was primarily established around large-scale, quantitative studies, based on the needs of political science and economics (Prandner et al., 2021, 5).

Given the inherently interdisciplinary character of the field of migration research, it is instrumental in determining the generation and accessibility of data that extends beyond the confines of quantitatively organised disciplines. As posited by Borgman (2010), Faniel and Jacobsen (2010) and Prandner (2023), there are discrepancies in the manner of data processing and the significance attributed to primary and secondary data, depending on the specific discipline. Consequently, any interdisciplinary research field must account for different needs.

It is a commonly held assumption amongst relevant authors that the researcher's disciplinary affiliation exerts a significant influence on the manner in which they utilise data infrastructures. This is due to the logics and attitudes that are specific to their discipline (Carlson and Anderson, 2007; Fane et al., 2016a; Federer et al., 2016; Prandner, 2023).

Recent research findings provide further evidence to support this observation. Although these findings are based on a single country, they reflect the results of recent research on the practices and attitudes of Austrian social researchers towards data infrastructures. A study undertaken in 2020 by Prandner, Hasengruber and Forstner (2021) posits that research conducted by economists and political scientists is still predominantly quantitative in nature. Secondary research is most frequently conducted by researchers from political science and sociology, with more than 60 percent of respondents in these fields. Moreover, the findings of Prandner et al. (2021) revealed that political scientists exhibited the highest level of acceptance in regard to the utilisation of external data, in comparison to social scientists from other disciplines. However, a cross-disciplinary analysis reveals that the distribution of Austrian social research pertaining to data collection methods appears to be relatively balanced. The survey data indicated that 34 per cent of respondents employed quantitative methods, 32 per cent utilised qualitative methods, and 26 per cent employed a combination of both quantitative and qualitative approaches for data collection. In relation to the data produced or utilised by social science for research purposes, the study indicates that transcribed qualitative interviews and data from official statistics are employed by 60% of the surveyed researchers. Furthermore, survey and text data, which can be used in quantitative and qualitative ways, are used by more than 50% of researchers. Consequently, these data are considered the most common (for details see Prandner et al., 2021: 5, 33pp).

A study undertaken for the Austrian Federal Ministries of the Interior and Women, Science and Research (previously known as the Federal Ministry for Education, Science and Research) in

parallel with the OPENMIN activities and with ties to the EMM survey registry also demonstrated that while 190 minority and migration-related data collections (see Prandner & Kern 2025a) based on quantitative research designs could be identified for the period between 2015 and 2024, 60 data collections with qualitative designs were created during the same period (see Prandner & Kern 2025b). The marked discrepancy is largely attributable to an extensive period of general population studies with longitudinal designs during the CoVid-19 crisis. These studies also addressed issues related to migrants to a certain extent and were consequently regarded as part of EMM research. Additionally, several survey study series going back as far as 2003 could be identified as well, which overall increased the number of quantitative survey studies, somewhat skewing the number of studies in favour of quantitative studies overall.

This illustration, based on a single country, demonstrates the necessity to construct a registry that prioritises the systematic documentation of qualitative studies through the utilisation of standardised metadata, as not only a substantive amount of studies could be identified, it was also harder to go back in time and find qualitative studies as they are seemingly more one-off studies. Adopting this approach has the potential to facilitate the identification of research gaps, support interoperability across research projects, and provide an evidence-based foundation for academic and socio-political debates.

Consequently, as part of Task 2.1 in the OPENMIN project, a standardised metadata schema was conceptualised and implemented for the prototype. This schema captures key characteristics of qualitative studies, including (but not limited to) methods of data collection, populations studied, thematic focus, geographical scope, and periods of data collection. Each entry in the registry is representative of a single qualitative study and the metadata associated with it.

2.1. Development process: Structure, Variables, Codes and Manuals

The development of the EMM Qualitative Studies Registry prototype required a preceding step — the design of a conceptual structure on which the database could be built. This structure drew heavily on the Ethnic and Migrant Minorities (EMM) Survey Data Hub Austria project, which had collected both qualitative and quantitative studies based on the logic and framework of the EMM Survey Registry (see: Morales & Saji 2021 as well as Morales et al.

2021). Building on this foundation, a manual was developed to enable the comprehensive mapping and documentation of qualitative studies. The variables and coding included into these manuals and the designs found in them underwent a series of iterative enhancements and changes during the course of the project, mainly through discussions between Jana Kern and the OpenMin Team, especially Andreas Perret from the University of Neuchâtel and Dimitrios Rafail Tservenis but also written feedback and support. All changes made to the preliminary variable list and manual considered the discussions; ensuring that the requirements of the community and the structured metadata could be accommodated. The current manual version can be found at Zenodo:

Dimitri, P., & Kern, J. (2026). *EMM Research Hub - Codebook and Template*. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18184987>

This manual serves as a detailed guide for entering, managing, and interpreting metadata within the registry. It follows the general logic and structure of the EMM Survey Registry while incorporating the experiences gained from the EMM Data Hub Austria research process.

Variable definitions, coding options, and descriptive elements were adapted to meet the particular requirements of qualitative research, while also trying hard to find links to existing metadata structures – particularly the DDI standard. Each section of the manual corresponds to a defined metadata block (e.g., study identification, sampling, data collection, or availability), ensuring conceptual coherence and facilitating comparability across studies.

The database mirrors this structure, providing standardized entry fields for all metadata variables defined in the manual. To test the usability, consistency, and logical flow of this system, a first dataset was created using Austrian qualitative studies on migration and ethnic minorities that had been previously mapped. This dataset was used to create entries and served as a means to verify the consistency of variable definitions, metadata relations, and the overall technical functionality within the registry environment.

By using this first data, inconsistencies, redundancies, and structural gaps could be identified early in the process. These findings informed several subsequent revisions of both the manual and the database template, ensuring closer alignment between conceptual design and technical implementation. The Austrian dataset ultimately demonstrated that the registry's core logic is functional and transferable to a production environment.

2.2. Development process: The structure of the registry and (re-)creating it within Dataverse

The registry structure developed is organised into nine thematic sections, each covering a distinct aspect of a study. The data entry process is facilitated by a dedicated interface, thereby ensuring the uniformity of documentation across various studies. The registry has been designed to be utilised by researchers, educators and policymakers operating within the domain of migration and minority studies. The fundamental design was derived from the EMM Survey Registry, which was developed by Laura Morales and Ami Saji (2021).

In the database each case (line) represents one study and its associated data. For every study, information on various aspects is recorded through an interface. Each section provides specific insights into the respective study

- **Section 1 – General Identification Information**

This section provides essential information to identify and classify datasets and projects. It includes study names, IDs, territorial scope, methods, and thematic focus, allowing users to track research developments over time.

- **Section 2 – Inclusion in Larger Study**

Here, users can record whether a project is part of a broader research program or related studies. It links subprojects and related data collections, ensuring traceability within multi-level or repeated research designs.

- **Section 3 – Target Population**

This section defines and describes the studied ethnic or migrant minority groups, including how they are operationalized. It helps identify which groups are represented in Austrian qualitative research and how they are categorized.

- **Section 4 – Sampling Method**

Details about the sampling strategy and design are provided here. This section helps assess data quality and understand how researchers accessed the target populations.

- **Section 5 – Sample Size**

Information about total and achieved sample sizes is recorded in this section. It supports evaluations of study scope and representativeness.

- **Section 7 – Data Collection Information**

This part documents how data were collected — methods used, interviewer characteristics, languages, and analysis techniques. It gives insight into fieldwork processes and methodological considerations.

- **Section 8 – Availability**

Information on data accessibility and repository links is summarized here. It specifies whether datasets or documentation are publicly available, restricted, or archived.

- **Section 9 – Data Producers, Owners, Distributors, and Citation**

This section identifies the institutions and researchers involved in producing, owning, and distributing the data. It also provides contact details and recommended dataset citations.

- **Section 10 – Additional Information**

Users can note limitations, data quality issues, and the sources of information here. It provides context for interpreting the reliability and scope of the metadata.

Additionally, structurally a sixth section “6 – Sample Size for Subgroups” exists, directly lifted from the EMM Survey Registry and pertains exclusively to quantitative data and is excluded from the current version of the study registry. It is retained as a placeholder for potential future adaptations or data integrations.

A full manual including specific description to the sections and included variables can be accessed here via the following DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17580353](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17580353)

Q1_4	Q1_5	Q1_6a	Q1_6b	Q1_7a
Women's Integration Survey	2	1	-999	-999,00 -999
Einstellung, Erwartungen und Ressourcen weiblicher Flüchtlinge	2	1	-999	-999,00 -999
Covid-19 und Migrationshintergrund	2	2	3	-999,00 Vienna
INREST (17/18)	2	2	1	-999,00 Styria
INREST (19)	2	2	1	-999,00 Styria
REFUGEEICT	2	2	3	-999,00 Vienna
Weibliche Asyl- und subsidiär Schutzberechtigte auf dem Arbeitsmarkt- Indormation, Mobilisierung und Int...	2	3	-999	2,00 -999
Covid-19 im Flucht- und Migrationskontext - Soziale Implikationen für die syrischen und afghanischen com...	2	2	3	-999,00 Vienna
Empowerment durch "Diaspora Entrepreneurship"	2	2	3	-999,00 Vienna
Integrationsverläufe asylberechtigter und subsidiär schutzberechtigter aus Aghanistan in Österreich	2	1	-999	-999,00 -999
(Mediale) Identitätskonstruktionen, transnationale Selbstverortungen & verkürzende Fremdzuschreibung...	2	2	3	-999,00 Vienna
-99	2	3	-999	4,00 -999
Die Kunst des Ankommens	2	-9	-999	-999,00 -999
De-Konstruktion von Differenz in der Sozialen Arbeit	2	1	-999	-999,00 -999
Active Urban Citizenship - von Utopien des Zusammenlebens zu einer nachhaltigen Stadtentwicklung	2	2	3	-999,00 Graz
Anerkennung und Partizipation von Migrant_innen. Ein Beitrag zur Verflüssigung von stereotypen Ausgrenz...	2	2	1	-999,00 Styria

Figure 3 - EMM Qualitative Studies Registry - Variableview

At the present stage, the development of the registry has reached an alpha-stage prototype. During the project's development phase, the emphasis was predominantly on conceptual design, schema definition, and functional testing, rather than on full-scale deployment. The evaluation of the registry primarily utilised mock data to assess its usability, structural integrity, and layout. Moreover, the empirical metadata from over 60 qualitative studies conducted in or related to Austria were systematically compiled, as those were identified. These data were prepared and made available via the EMMSD² tool (see also D2.2, for Task 2.2) in the context of the OpenMin project. In conjunction with the dataset, a comprehensive manual for metadata coding was produced and published:

Prandner, Dimitri; Kern, Jana (2025). EMM Research Hub Austria (qualitative) (SUF edition), AUSSDA. <https://doi.org/10.11587/ZZPCXX/XQQHPX>

At present, access to the registry prototype is restricted to AUSSDA members, who are able to directly access, edit and expand the database in the Dataverse sandbox hosted by AUSSDA at the university of Vienna.

In order to allow for greater participation, an Excel-based metadata template was developed, based on the template that was originally developed by Morales and Saji (2021) for the EMM survey registry. The template has been designed to be used in combination with the coding manual, with the objective of enabling external contributors to prepare metadata in a standardised format. This was also used to create the dataset cited previously on the situation in Austria.

In the future interested users are invited to submit completed Excel templates to the project team. Submissions will be subjected to a rigorous quality control process, and contributors

may be requested to make necessary revisions. Once entries have been validated, they can be integrated as new datasets in the EMMSD² tool (see Deliverable 2.2, Task 2.2) and serve as a basis for future expansions. This allows for the long-term storage of data that is collected within the currently developed framework for an upcoming qualitative studies registry that would enter production status. As the datasets are preserved by the regulations of AUSSDA in the EMMSD² tool, the hosting and long-term preservation is guaranteed that way until a full-scale registry can be fielded.

The main idea is that these datasets entered into the registry can be extracted and used to gain an overall understanding of the field. This path allows both for a quantitative analysis and at the same time, it is possible to focus on a single case to obtain an overview of that specific study, including its methods, thematic focus, and linked documents.

For example, if one would like to know how many of the listed qualitative studies use interviews, one can analyse variable 1.11 from section one, gaining an insight into the current composition of the data landscape in the field. However, in light of resource constraints, the development of a comprehensive public web interface that would facilitate direct browsing and querying of the registry via a web browser is currently neither planned nor feasible. Further development would require additional funding and infrastructural support that extends beyond the scope of the present project.

				Percentage (case based)
		N	Percentage	
Method of Data Collection	1.11.1 Individual Interviews	53	53,0%	81,5%
	1.11.2 Groupinterviews	21	21,0%	32,3%
	1.11.3 Survey	2	2,0%	3,1%
	1.11.4 Structural or register data	2	2,0%	3,1%
	1.11.5 Content analysis	10	10,0%	15,4%
	1.11.7 Observation	5	5,0%	7,7%
	1.11.8 Other	7	7,0%	10,8%
Overall		100	100,0%	153,8%

Tab. 1 - Data analysis based on data collected for the prototype (Only Austrian projects)

2.3. Test Phase and Use of the AUSSDA Dataverse

The final step concerning the prototype was the structure to create a working dataverse environment that allowed to enter the data as described in the manual and the already present dataset. In the first step, a test Dataverse was created to explore the possibilities and

limitations of the project. For this purpose, the existing AUSSDA repository was used as a host platform.

This choice offered several advantages:

First, the existing infrastructure allowed us to test the repository within an already established and fully functioning environment. This meant that we did not have to build a new system from scratch but could instead build upon existing structures and workflows.

The AUSSDA repository provides functionality for uploading scientific data and accompanying research documentation, making them both discoverable and clearly structured through the provision of comprehensive metadata on its website. While most datasets are uploaded and curated by AUSSDA itself, the repository also includes a self-deposit service that enables external users to create their own data entries. This self-deposit environment was used as the foundation for our implementation. It registers all relevant metadata fields in the same way as other AUSSDA entries. Within this repository, a specific template was built with the help of AUSSDA to integrate the structure of the EMM qualitative studies registry into the existing metadata framework.

Secondly, we benefited from the extensive expertise already present within the AUSSDA team, which substantially supported both the technical configuration and the practical implementation of the repository. Especially the local tech officer, Christian Bischof, who was responsible for programming and defining the dataverse structure within AUSSDA.

However, while there is a certain degree of conceptual overlap between the registry set up and the structure of the traditional AUSSDA dataverse, several issues became evident during programming: their reliance on different metadata standards and structural logics leads to redundancies, inconsistencies, and a certain lack of clarity within the overall metadata framework. These issues would need to be further refined and harmonized in subsequent development stages.

Especially when the data collected should remain linkable to other data from the EMM project, this becomes a major issue. When using an already existing Dataverse, the structure and formatting of the data would have to be modified to comply with its standards. As a result, any later linkage back to existing EMM quantitative data or other EMM datasets would require a very time-consuming and complex process.

The screenshot shows the AUSSDA website interface. At the top, the AUSSDA logo and name are displayed alongside navigation links for Search, About, and User Guide. The main heading is 'Integration of Refugees in Styrian Companies (17/18)', with 'Draft' and 'Unpublished' status indicators. Below the title, there is a document icon and a text box containing the citation: 'University of Graz, 2025, "Integration of Refugees in Styrian Companies (17/18)", <https://doi.org/10.0250/WB9CPS>, AUSSDA, DRAFT VERSION'. There are links for 'Cite Dataset' and 'Learn about Data Citation Standards'. A 'Description' section follows, stating: 'Studying labour market integration of refugees based on semi-structured interviews with 97 refugees and their work environment.' The 'Keyword' is 'Integration, Employment'. The 'License/Data Use Agreement' section shows a copyright notice: 'Copyright. All rights reserved'. At the bottom, there are tabs for 'Files', 'Metadata', 'Terms', and 'Versions', and three expandable metadata sections: 'Citation Metadata', 'Social Science and Humanities Metadata', and 'EMM Metadata'.

Figure 4 - EMM Qualitative Studies Registry

3. Target Group, Scope and Use Case

The primary target demographic comprises social scientists specialising in qualitative research who are engaged in the field of migration and minority-focused studies. These individuals are interested in enhancing the visibility of their research projects and contributing to the establishment of a comprehensive overview of the current state of research in this domain.

Nonetheless, the instrument is not yet prepared for deployment in a production version. At present, only a structure for the data collection and a prototype of the database are available. These could be utilised to identify issues and problems during OPENMIN.

The present use case is to demonstrate the potential and structure of such a registry, whilst simultaneously highlighting the limitations that are concomitant with it.

The technology officer, Christian Bischof, at AUSSDA has expressed a number of concerns regarding the utilisation of the Dataverse infrastructure for the registry. Firstly, the system

requires constant management and maintenance. Consequently, it is only feasible when it can be integrated into a running dataverse instance. Nevertheless, the emphasis on metadata complicates the process of replicating existing structures, such as those found in the Dataverse installations within CESSDA. This is due to the fact that only a proportion of the data would be compatible, with a significant amount being deemed unsuitable for harvesting due to its incompatibility with the logic of existing data catalogues. Moreover, the functions of a Dataverse are associated with the hosting of microdata (i.e. actual research data in numeric or string format). Consequently, the functions of a Dataverse may be excessive and result in data clutter. Accordingly, he proposed that in the event of further development of the tool being planned, with the objective of creating a functional version for deployment, consideration should be given to the integration of a version that also provides a means of storing microdata and making it available. In the absence of such integration, the cost and resources associated with Dataverse-use as software solution may prove to be economically unviable.

Moreover, the capacity of Dataverse is constrained in terms of its ability to display and adapt to the requirements of the web front end. Consequently, the engagement of a dedicated designer and programmer is imperative to engineer a web interface that can be customized to align with the specifications of such a registry. In light of the aforementioned points, he further suggested that it may be necessary to adjust and ensure that a single registry is implemented for all types of studies, based on a uniform software foundation (even if web interfaces are divided), in order to address all technical requirements concurrently.

4. Screenshots and Insights into the Prototype

This section gives insights into how the Dataverse prototype is currently set up and the problems associated with it:

The screenshot shows the 'Social Science and Humanities Metadata' section of the Dataverse Registry Data Entry form. The 'EMM Metadata' section includes the following fields:

- 1.5. Territorial scope of the study: Sub-national
- 1.6a. If subnational, which level?: federal state
- 1.6b. If transnational, which level?: Not applicable
- 1.8a.2 If subnational, type of subnational area?: Don't know
- 1.9. Is the study designed to be 'representative' of the (sub)population in this territory?: No
- 1.11 What method of data collection was used for this study?: Individual interviews
- 1.11.a. If other in 1.11 specify: (empty text area with a plus sign)
- 1.12a. Other Time Method (Social Science and Humanities Metadata: Time Method): (empty text area with a plus sign)
- 1.13a. Starting date of project: 2017

Figure 5 - The first section of the Registry Data Entry in Dataverse

The screenshot shows the continuation of the Dataverse Registry Data Entry form. The fields include:

- 1.13a. Starting date of project: 2017
- 1.14a. End date of project: 2018
- 1.15 Study is still in development/ not yet completed: Completed
- 1.16. Main topic(s) covered by the study: Asylum seekers and refugee issues, Educational attainment/trajectory, human capital, skills, Interethnic contact and conflict, Labour market integration
- 1.16a. If other in 1.16, specify: (empty text area with a plus sign)
- 1.17. Main purpose of the study: Research/academic
- 1.17a. If other in 1.17, specify: (empty text area with a plus sign)
- 1.18. What is the coverage of the target population in terms of age?: Adult population (18+ or 15+) only

Figure 6 - Continuation of entry. Topics based on multiple choice selection during entry and display as tags on frontend. the issue is 1.16a, as this can not be converted into Tags.

2.7. In case of repeated/longitudinal studies: Which wave number corresponds to this study register? ?	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="+"/>
2.8. In the case of studies that are part of an international study programme ?	<input type="text" value="YYYY"/>	
2.9. In the case of studies that are part of an international study programme: Frequency of waves since then ?	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="+"/>
2.10. If sample is pooled: how many studies pooled. ?	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="+"/>
2.11. If sample is pooled: which other studies pooled. ?	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="+"/>
2.11a. If sample is pooled, does the sample include emigrants from more than one country? ?	<input type="text" value="Select.."/>	
2.12. Any other qualitative or quantitative studies linked to the study? ?	<input type="text" value="Select.."/>	
2.12a Name or Case number of study ?	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="+"/>
2.13. If yes, please describe these studies ?	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="+"/>
2.14 Comments relevant to	<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="+"/>

Figure 7 - Danger of an open questions and entry fields. Chance for user-error.

3.1. EMM Target population: which minority group(s) ?	Refugees from Afghanistan, Syria, Iraq with asylum status, seeking for asylum or being denied the asylum status but with suspended deportation
3.1a. EMM target population with terms standardized ?	Refugees
3.2. Was the EMM target population... ?	A selection of residents of foreign/migrant origin or ancestry in the city/region/country
3.3. How is target population defined / operationalized / identified ?	Citizenship/nationality of respondent (current); Administrative/legal status
3.4. Migrant / minority related questions in the questionnaire ?	Nationality of respondent (current)
3.6. Does the study include a subgroup of majority/autochthonous/ general population? ?	No
3.6a Study designed as a general population study ?	No
4.2. Sampling strategy – open-ended (Social Science and Humanities Metadata: Sampling Procedure) ?	Convenience sample
4.3. Sample design – full additional information ?	Convenience sample based on personal connection, Cooperationnetworks, snowballmethod, media presence or events with focus on non academic fields

Figure 8 - Sections 3 and 4, long structure makes it necessary to create sub-fields with new variables. Sorting may not be perfect when structure is taken from database in the background

information on the sampling method ?	<input type="text"/>	-
7a. Name of methodological sub-part ?	<input type="text" value="Refugee Interviews"/>	+
7.2a. Other type of data (Citation: Data Type) ?	<input type="text"/>	+
7.3. For personal interviews: who interviewed? ?	<input type="text" value="Don't know"/>	-
7.4. For personal interviews: interviewers spoke migrant or ethnic minority group languages? ?	<input type="text" value="Yes"/>	-
7.4a. If yes, which? (separated by a semicolon) ?	<input type="text" value="Arabic"/>	+
7.5. Average duration/length of interview ?	<input type="text"/>	+
7.6. For other methods of data collection, which language is the data collected in (separated by a semicolon) ?	<input type="text"/>	+

Figure 9 - Standardization needs to be applied on a Dataverse level. This would be a core issue for the next iteration of the tool. Replacing free text fields with selection-based ones, e.g. for countries, languages etc.

5. Beyond Microdata: Metadata, Persistent Identification, FAIR Principles and Quality Assurance

One of the core objectives of the task was to ascertain the necessity of metadata for the description of qualitative studies, with a view to ensuring that such metadata met the requirements of the community and adhered to established international standards, such as DDI.

The identified metadata, which is used to describe the study design, data collection process, variable structure, documentation, and access conditions, should be made available through the Dataverse interface once the tool reaches production status, which it does not at the present time. Nevertheless, measures are being implemented to ensure that each entry into the registry can be identified and traced. In order to guarantee stable referencing, citations and long-term findability, it has been decided that a persistent Digital Object Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to each. In the absence of a viable option to assign each entry a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), it was determined that a solution would be sought for the allocation of each country dataset, akin to the one developed for Austria during the prototyping stage, as a singular DOI. This approach would ensure that each country database fulfils the criteria for FAIR (findability, accessibility, inter-operability, and reusability).

The management of these metadata collections could then be undertaken by the hosts of the Dataverse, with the implementation of role-based access control mechanisms within the Dataverse infrastructure.

The metadata that is deposited would be subject to quality audits, which would be conducted by staff members who have received training on this subject. However, it should be noted that this would require a significant investment of personal resources.

6. Timeline of the development of the prototype during OPENMIN

The development of the tool was divided into three phases.

The first step was purely conceptual, involving the definition of an expected feature set. Next, the tool was proposed to the relevant stakeholders in Austria, including the legal department of Johannes Kepler University, the national AUSSDA leadership board, and Lars Kaczmirek, the head of AUSSDA, who is based at the University of Vienna. This had to be done to ensure that all AUSSDA and university-level data protection regulations can be adhered to and necessary resources for the project can be allocated. Dimitri Prandner subsequently visited the project partners of OpenMin at the University of Neuchâtel in late 2024, where he was presented with information on database construction and the creation of interactive data tools by Andreas Perret. The utilisation of the aforementioned information was instrumental in facilitating a deliberative discourse on prospective solutions for the implementation of the Dataverse with Christian Bischof, AUSSDA's technical officer, and Jana Kern, a research associate involved in the aforementioned project for the Austrian Ministry of the Interior.

The second phase, during the the winter of 2024 and 2025, consisted of developing a catalogue of variables for the EMM qualitative studies registry and mapping variables to the DDI format. Jana Kern was entrusted with this responsibility of under the supervision of Dimitri Prandner. After this, she engaged with the OpenMin team on feedback in the Summer of 2025. Subsequently, a detailed description of the metadata was furnished, and an Excel spreadsheet was devised for the systematic collection of metadata.

Following the collection of data from 60 studies the third phase started as Jana Kern and Christian Bischof initiated the process of transferring selected metadata of a small number of studies into the designated Dataverse infrastructure. Concurrently, they commenced the documentation of potential issues and initiated a discussion on the subject. It was determined that while feasible, transitioning from the prototype stage to the production

version would necessitate a substantial investment in terms of both financial resources and human capital. This investment would be accompanied by the development of automated tools and interfaces to automatically transfer data into the Dataverse in the correct formats and forms. The primary objective of these tools and interfaces would be to facilitate both the efficient addition of data and the creation of a user-friendly navigation experience for potential users.

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